

Integrative Approaches for Analyzing Physicochemical and Biological Data for Water Quality Monitoring of Khairatabad Lake

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Abstract

Water is the driving force of nature, sustaining ecosystems, human life, and daily activities. Growing population, rapid urbanization, and pollution have increased pressure on freshwater systems, contributing to a condition of “water bankruptcy” in many regions. Lakes are important freshwater reservoirs that support local biodiversity, fisheries, and drinking water supply. However, they face severe contamination from human activity which degrades their quality. This study focuses on Khairatabad Lake, an urban water body hydrologically linked with Hussain Sagar Lake in Hyderabad, Telangana, which is continuously affected by anthropogenic activities such as fishing, recreation, surface runoff, and domestic waste discharge. Despite its environmental significance and visible human use, it has received comparatively limited scientific attention, emphasizing the need for focused water quality evaluation. An integrative approach was employed to evaluate the water quality through physicochemical, microbial, and biochemical analyses. Physicochemical parameters were measured and evaluated against the Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS) and World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines, while microbial and biochemical analyses characterized contamination and metabolic activity. The suitability of the lake water for human consumption and aquatic life was assessed and the findings reveal urbanization's significant impact on the ecological health of the lake, highlighting poor water quality, and urging targeted interventions to mitigate anthropogenic pressures.

Keywords: *Khairatabad Lake, Physicochemical Parameters, Bureau of Indian Standards, Biochemical Analyses, Microbial Contamination.*

Introduction

Water is indispensable for life and for maintaining ecological equilibrium. However, accessible freshwater represents a very small share of the planet's total water reserves, as the overwhelming majority exists in saline form within oceans (Scanlon et al., 2023). Increasing withdrawal to meet domestic, agricultural, and industrial demands has placed considerable stress on river basins and aquifers, in some cases exceeding their natural recharge capacity. This imbalance has led to concerns of a growing global “water bankruptcy,” where water use surpasses sustainable limits (Madani, 2026). Despite advancements in infrastructure and policy, significant portion of

the global population still lacks dependable access to safe drinking water, reinforcing the urgency for improved resource management.

Water Pollution

Beyond issues of availability, deterioration in water quality presents an equally serious challenge. Human activities introduce a complex mixture of chemical, physical, and biological contaminants into freshwater systems. Industrial effluents contain toxic metals and synthetic compounds, while agricultural drainage often transports nutrient surpluses and pesticide residues. Expanding urban settlements contribute untreated sewage, microbial pathogens, and solid waste inputs (Izah & Ogwu, 2026). Through interconnected surface and subsurface pathways within the hydrological cycle, these contaminants disperse and accumulate, progressively altering ecosystem structure and function (Shekhar et al., 2024).

The implications extend to public health; Contact with polluted water is associated not only with acute infections but also with longer-term health effects. Emerging epidemiological evidence suggests potential links between environmental contamination and cardiovascular as well as systemic disorders (Münzel et al., 2025). Contamination is not always visually apparent, as harmful substances may be present even when water appears clear. Consequently, routine laboratory-based monitoring remains essential to accurately evaluate water safety and safeguard ecological integrity (K?l?ç, 2020).

Water Quality Analysis

Water quality assessment involves integrated evaluation of physicochemical and biological parameters. These parameters are compared against standards prescribed by regulatory bodies such as the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS). Exceeding permissible limits may adversely affect human health and aquatic ecosystems (Sharma & Kumar, 2016).

Key Physicochemical Parameters for Analysis of Water Quality

Assessment of water quality requires evaluation of physicochemical parameters that collectively reflect ecosystem stability and pollution load. Rather than functioning independently, these parameters interact dynamically and influence biological productivity, microbial activity, and overall ecological balance.

Water temperature plays a regulatory role in chemical reaction rates and microbial metabolism, directly affecting dissolved oxygen availability. Variations beyond natural seasonal limits can intensify oxygen depletion and stress aquatic organisms. pH of the water indicates its acid–base status and governs nutrient solubility, and biochemical processes. Slightly alkaline conditions are typical in productive freshwater systems; however, substantial deviations may signal contamination or altered buffering capacity. Bicarbonate concentration contributes to the alkalinity of freshwater bodies, stabilizing pH against sudden chemical fluctuations.

Turbidity reflects the degree of suspended particulate matter, including organic debris and microbial populations. Elevated turbidity reduces light penetration, limiting photosynthetic efficiency and potentially enhancing pathogen persistence. Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) provide insight into the dissolved inorganic and organic substances. Increasing TDS levels often indicate urban runoff, wastewater intrusion, or evaporative concentration, all of which may alter osmotic balance in aquatic life.

Oxygen-related parameters serve as critical indicators of organic pollution. Dissolved Oxygen (DO) reflects the balance between oxygen production and consumption within the system (Verma et al., 2025). Biochemical

Oxygen Demand (BOD) estimates the extent of biodegradable organic matter present in the lake, indicating microbial oxygen consumption (Lee & An, 2014), whereas Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) represents the total oxidizable load, including non-biodegradable components (Latif & Dickert, 2015). Discrepancies between BOD and COD values help differentiate between predominantly biological and mixed pollution sources.

Distribution of Water Supply in Hyderabad

Until the 1930s, Hussain Sagar Lake served as the primary source for drinking water and irrigation. Constructed in 1562 during the reign of Ibrahim Quli Qutb Shah, it originally functioned as a storage reservoir (Rafi & Kusum, 2018). Over time, it has become a major ecological and recreational landmark.

Rapid urbanization has placed considerable environmental stress on the Hussain Sagar basin. The lake receives inflows from major feeder drains that transport domestic sewage, stormwater runoff, and industrial effluents. Continuous nutrient enrichment and organic loading have contributed to water quality deterioration, eutrophication, and ecological imbalance (Prakash et al., 2021).

Study Focus: Khairatabad Lake

The current study focuses on Khairatabad Lake, an urban water body hydrologically linked to Hussain Sagar but represents a localized zone subjected to intense anthropogenic pressure in the form of fishing, recreational use, surface runoff influx, and domestic waste discharge, which increase the likelihood of contamination.

Despite being part of the larger lake system, the Khairatabad stretch has received comparatively limited scientific attention. Spatial heterogeneity within urban lakes often leads to significant variation in pollutant distribution and ecological responses. Therefore, site-specific assessment is necessary for accurate environmental evaluation.

Materials and Methods

Sample Collection and Physical Analysis

Surface water samples were collected from Khairatabad Lake, using sterile, airtight containers. On-site measurements of physical parameters was performed to minimize variability.

Chemical Analysis

Chemical parameters were analyzed following standard titrimetric procedures and compared with permissible limits prescribed by the Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS).

Estimation of Ammonia

Ammonia concentration was estimated by acid titration. Water sample was treated with methyl orange indicator and titrated against N/10 hydrochloric acid until a pale yellow to pink endpoint was observed. Ammonia content was calculated from the titration values.

Estimation of Bicarbonates

Bicarbonate alkalinity was determined by titrating the water sample with N/20 sulphuric acid using methyl orange as indicator. The endpoint was marked by a colour change from pale yellow to orange.

Determination of Total Hardness

Total hardness, attributed to calcium and magnesium ions, was determined by EDTA complexometric titration. Water sample was buffered to pH 10 using ammoniacal buffer and titrated against 0.1 M EDTA using Eriochrome Black T (EBT) as indicator. The endpoint was indicated by a color change from wine red to blue.

Estimation of Zinc

Zinc concentration was estimated by EDTA titration. Water sample was buffered with ammoniacal buffer and titrated against 0.1 M EDTA using EBT indicator until a wine red to blue endpoint was obtained.

Determination of Dissolved Oxygen (DO)

Dissolved oxygen was determined using the Winkler iodometric method. Water sample was collected in stoppered bottles without air bubbles. Manganese sulphate and alkaline iodide reagents were added to fix dissolved oxygen. After acidification with sulphuric acid, the liberated iodine was titrated against standardized sodium thiosulphate using starch as indicator until the blue colour disappeared. DO concentration was calculated from the titration values.

Determination of Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD)

Biochemical Oxygen Demand was determined by incubating water sample in a sealed bottle for 5 days in the dark. Dissolved oxygen was measured initially and after incubation using the Winkler method. BOD₅ was calculated as the difference between initial and final DO values.

Determination of Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD)

COD was determined using the dichromate reflux method. Water sample was digested with potassium dichromate under acidic conditions in a water bath at 100°C for one hour. After cooling, potassium iodide was added and the liberated iodine was titrated against standardized sodium thiosulphate using starch indicator. COD values were calculated from the titration readings.

Microbiological Analysis

Enrichment and Culture

Water sample was inoculated into sterile nutrient broth and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours to obtain bacterial enrichment culture.

Gram Staining

Loopful of culture was heat-fixed onto clean glass slide and subjected to Gram staining using crystal violet, Gram's iodine, alcohol decolorization, and safranin counterstaining. Slide was air-dried and examined under a compound microscope.

Streaking on Selective and Differential Media

Enriched culture was streaked onto Eosin Methylene Blue (EMB) agar and MacConkey agar plates. Plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours.

Biochemical Characterization

Catalase Test

A drop of hydrogen peroxide was added to a loopful of culture placed on a glass slide. Immediate effervescence indicated a positive reaction.

Oxidase Test

A loopful of culture was streaked onto oxidase disc and observed for colour change indicating oxidase enzyme activity.

Hydrogen Sulphide (H₂S) Production

Loopful of culture was inoculated onto Kligler's Iron Agar slants and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. After incubation, the agar slants were observed for colour change.

IMViC Tests

IMViC profile is a series of four tests performed to differentiate enteric bacteria.

- Indole Test: Culture was incubated in tryptophan broth for 24 hours at 37°C and tested for indole production using Kovac’s reagent.
- Methyl Red Test: Culture was incubated in MR-VP broth for 24 hours at 37°C and treated with methyl red indicator to assess mixed acid fermentation.
- Voges-Proskauer Test: Culture was incubated in MR-VP broth for 24 hours at 37°C and treated with α -naphthol and potassium hydroxide to detect acetoin production.
- Citrate Utilisation Test: Loopful of culture was streaked on Simmons citrate agar and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. Colour change from green to blue indicates citrate utilisation.

Results

Sample Collection

Figure 1: Site of sample collection (left) Turbidity of water sample (right)

Physical Analysis of water sample

Physical Parameter	Value Observed	BIS
pH	7.9	6.5-8.5
Temperature	25.7°C	10-20°C
Total Dissolved Solids (TDS)	423 ppm	500 mg/L

Chemical Analysis of water sample

Chemical Parameter	Value Observed	BIS
Ammonia	0.179 mg/L	0.5 mg/L
Bicarbonates	152 ppm	200 ppm
Total Hardness (Ca, Mg)	Ca = 0.16 mg/L, Mg = 0.09 mg/L	75 mg/L; 30 mg/L
Zinc	0.261 mg/L	5.0 mg/L
Dissolved Oxygen	4.36 mg/L	6.5-8 mg/L

Gram Staining of Bacterial Culture isolated from water sample

Figure 2: Purple and Pink colonies observed under light microscope

Streaking of Bacteria isolated from the water sample

Figure 3: Growth of Dark Colonies with metallic green sheen on EMB Agar Plate (left) and Pink Colour Colonies on MacConkey Agar Plate (right)

Catalase Test

Figure 4: Formation of effervescence by culture after addition of Hydrogen Peroxide

Oxidase Test

Figure 5: Purple colour observed a few seconds after culture was streaked onto oxidase disc

Hydrogen Sulphide Production

Figure 6: Black precipitate formation indicates H₂S production.

IMViC Tests

Fig 7: Results indicating (i) Red ring formation in Indole test, (ii) Red Colouration in Methyl Red test, and negative reactions for (iii) Voges–Proskauer and (iv) Citrate utilization tests.

Discussion

The present study aimed to assess the physicochemical characteristics of Khairatabad Lake water, identify microbial species present, and evaluate the overall suitability and ecological health of the lake ecosystem by comparing the results with Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS) guidelines.

The physicochemical assessment revealed moderate deviations from BIS standards, indicating emerging ecological stress. The sample exhibited noticeable turbidity, which reduces light penetration, limits photosynthetic activity, and may facilitate pathogen survival. The recorded pH fell within the acceptable BIS range, indicating slightly alkaline yet chemically stable conditions. This alkalinity may be attributed to bicarbonate buffering and biological productivity within the lake.

The observed temperature exceeded the recommended range, which can significantly influence dissolved oxygen solubility and microbial metabolism. Elevated temperatures enhance microbial respiration and biochemical reaction rates, thereby increasing oxygen demand. Total Dissolved Solids remained within the BIS limit, suggesting moderate mineralization; however, continuous urban runoff may elevate these levels over time.

Ammonia concentration was below the permissible limit, indicating limited recent sewage intrusion or active nitrification. Nonetheless, its presence reflects ongoing organic matter decomposition. Bicarbonate concentration was within acceptable limits, confirming adequate buffering capacity against abrupt pH fluctuations. Calcium and magnesium concentrations were significantly below BIS thresholds, indicating low hardness and minimal mineral stress. Zinc levels were well below the permissible limit, suggesting limited heavy metal contamination at the sampling site.

In contrast, oxygen-related parameters indicated ecological imbalance. Dissolved Oxygen was below the recommended range, reflecting oxygen depletion likely due to organic matter degradation. Biochemical Oxygen Demand slightly exceeded the acceptable limit, signifying increased biodegradable organic load. More notably, Chemical Oxygen Demand exceeded the BIS standard, indicating the presence of substantial oxidizable organic pollutants, including non-biodegradable fractions. The disparity between BOD and COD values suggests a mixed pollution profile, likely influenced by domestic sewage discharge and urban runoff. Collectively, reduced DO and elevated BOD and COD confirm moderate organic pollution and ecosystem stress within the lake.

Microbiological analysis further substantiated anthropogenic impact. Gram staining revealed both Gram-positive (purple) and Gram-negative (pink) bacterial populations, indicating microbial diversity. The presence of Gram-negative bacteria is commonly associated with enteric organisms and fecal contamination.

Streaking on EMB agar produced dark colonies with a characteristic metallic green sheen, strongly suggestive of *Escherichia coli*. EMB agar is selective for Gram-negative bacteria and

differential based on lactose fermentation. MacConkey agar, which is selective for Gram-negative enteric bacteria, yielded pink colonies, further confirming lactose fermentation and supporting the presence of coliform organisms.

Biochemical characterization reinforced these findings. Immediate effervescence in the catalase test confirmed catalase activity, indicating the organism's ability to decompose hydrogen peroxide. The oxidase test showed a purple coloration, indicating cytochrome c oxidase activity; however, since classical *E. coli* is oxidase-negative, this result suggests the presence of mixed bacterial populations. Black precipitate formation in Kligler's Iron Agar confirmed hydrogen sulphide (H₂S) production, demonstrating sulphur metabolism typical of certain enteric bacteria. IMViC profile (Indole positive, Methyl Red positive, Voges–Proskauer negative, Citrate negative) corresponds to the characteristic (++--) pattern of *Escherichia coli*.

Indole positivity confirms tryptophan degradation, while Methyl Red positivity indicates stable acid production via mixed acid fermentation. Negative Voges–Proskauer and citrate tests further differentiate *E. coli* from other Enterobacteriaceae species.

The confirmed presence of coliform bacteria indicates fecal contamination and renders the water microbiologically unsafe for direct human consumption without adequate treatment. These findings strongly suggest the influence of urban runoff, sewage inflow, and sustained anthropogenic activities.

Conclusion

This study applied an integrative approach combining physicochemical and microbiological analyses to evaluate the water quality of Khairatabad Lake. Comparison with Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS) guidelines revealed that while several physicochemical parameters remained within permissible limits, oxygen-related indicators reflected ecological stress. Reduced dissolved oxygen and elevated BOD and COD values indicated moderate organic pollution and increased oxygen demand, likely resulting from urban runoff and domestic wastewater inputs.

Microbiological analysis confirmed the presence of coliform bacteria, with culture characteristics and IMViC profiling consistent with *Escherichia coli*, indicating fecal contamination. The detection of lactose-fermenting enteric bacteria renders the water microbiologically unsuitable for direct human consumption without treatment.

Collectively, the findings demonstrate that reliance on physicochemical parameters alone may underestimate water quality risks. The integration of chemical, physical, and biological indicators provides a more comprehensive and realistic assessment of ecosystem health. Although the lake does not exhibit severe heavy metal or mineral contamination, organic loading and microbial presence indicate moderate anthropogenic impact. Continuous monitoring and targeted management interventions are essential to mitigate pollution sources and safeguard the ecological integrity and public health value of this urban freshwater system.

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